

RESEARCH ON 3D PRINTING DESIGN EDUCATION AND INDUSTRY-EDUCATION INTEGRATION IN CHINA: A CASE STUDY OF GUANGZHOU POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY

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Annotatsiya. *Ishlab chiqarish sanoatining raqamli transformatsiyasini harakatlantiruvchi asosiy texnologiya sifatida, additiv ishlab chiqarish (3D bosib chiqarish) Xitoy sanoatining jadal rivojlanishiga turki berdi, shu bilan birga fanlararo texnik va malakali mutaxassislar uchun katta bo'shliqni yaratdi. An'anaviy kasb-hunar ta'limi fanlararo tarqoqlik, o'qitish va sanoat amaliyoti o'rtasidagi uzilish hamda o'quv dasturlarining eskirishi kabi muammolardan aziyat chekmoqda. Shunday qilib, sanoat va ta'lim integratsiyasi iste'dodlarga bo'lgan talab va taklif o'rtasidagi tafovutni bartaraf etish hamda ta'lim zanjirini sanoat zanjiri bilan muvofiqlashtirishning hal qiluvchi yondashuviga aylandi. Guanchjou politexnika universitetini misol tariqasida olib, ushbu maqolada uning 3D bosib chiqarish dizayni ta'limidagi amaliyoti tahlil qilinadi, jumladan Kelajak texnologiyalari institutini tashkil etish, "korxonalar muammolarni taklif qiladi, universitetlar yechimlarni taqdim etadi va bozor baholaydi" innovatsion hamkorlik mexanizmi, o'quv dasturlarini dinamik ogohlantirish tizimini qurish, shuningdek sanoat kollejlari va buyurtma asosidagi kadrlar tayyorlash dasturlarini birgalikda tashkil etish. Unda kadrlar tayyorlash, texnologik innovatsiyalar va natijalarni joriy etish sohasidagi yutuqlar sarhisob qilinadi, texnologiyalarning tezkor o'zgarishi, intellektual mulkni taqsimlashning nomukammalligi va fanlararo o'qituvchilar yetishmasligi kabi sanoat-ta'lim integratsiyasidagi muammolar aniqlanadi hamda o'quv dasturlarini tezkor yangilash, foydani taqsimlash mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish va to'rt tomonlama o'zaro hamkorlik ekotizimini chuqurlashtirish kabi optimallashtirish yo'llari taklif etiladi. Ushbu tadqiqot Xitoy bo'ylab kasb-hunar kollejlari 3D bosib chiqarish ta'limi va sanoat hamkorligi uchun takrorlanadigan (replicable) paradigma yaratishni maqsad qilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *3D bosib chiqarish; additiv ishlab chiqarish; sanoat va ta'lim integratsiyasi; kasb-hunar ta'limi; kadrlar tayyorlash; Guanchjou politexnika universiteti*

Аннотация. *Аддитивное производство (3D-печать) как ключевая технология цифровой трансформации обрабатывающей промышленности способствовало быстрому развитию промышленности Китая, одновременно создав значительный дефицит междисциплинарных технических и квалифицированных специалистов. Традиционное профессиональное образование страдает от дисциплинарной раздробленности, разрыва между обучением и промышленной практикой, а также отставания в обновлении учебных программ. Таким образом, интеграция промышленности и образования стала важнейшим путем к преодолению разрыва между спросом и предложением талантов и согласованию образовательной цепочки с промышленной. На примере Гуанчжоуского политехнического университета в данной статье анализируется его практика в области образования по 3D-дизайну, включая создание Института технологий будущего, инновационный механизм сотрудничества по принципу «предприятия ставят задачи, университеты находят решения, а рынок оценивает результаты», построение динамической системы раннего предупреждения учебных планов, а также совместное создание отраслевых институтов*

и программ подготовки кадров под конкретные заказы. В работе обобщены достижения в области подготовки кадров, технологических инноваций и трансформации достижений, выявлены проблемы текущей интеграции, такие как быстрая итерация технологий, несовершенство распределения интеллектуальной собственности и нехватка междисциплинарных преподавателей, а также предложены пути оптимизации, включая гибкое обновление учебных программ, совершенствование механизмов распределения выгод и углубление экосистемы четырехстороннего взаимодействия. Данное исследование направлено на создание воспроизводимой парадигмы для образования в области 3D-печати и промышленного сотрудничества в профессиональных колледжах по всему Китаю.

Ключевые слова: 3D-печать; аддитивное производство; интеграция промышленности и образования; профессиональное образование; подготовка кадров; Гуанчжоуский политехнический университет

Abstract. As a core technology driving the digital transformation of the manufacturing industry, additive manufacturing (3D printing) has fueled the rapid development of China's industries while creating a substantial gap for interdisciplinary technical and skilled professionals. Traditional vocational education is plagued by disciplinary fragmentation, the disjuncture between teaching and industrial practice, and lagging curriculum updates. Industry-education integration has thus become a critical approach to bridging the talent supply-demand gap and aligning the education chain with the industrial chain. Taking Guangzhou Polytechnic University as a case study, this paper analyzes its practices in 3D printing design education, including the establishment of a Future Technology Institute, the innovative collaborative mechanism of "enterprises propose problems, universities provide solutions, and the market conducts evaluation", the construction of a dynamic curriculum early warning system, and the co-construction of industrial colleges and order-based talent cultivation programs. It summarizes the achievements in talent cultivation, technological innovation, and achievement transformation, identifies the challenges in current industry-education integration such as rapid technological iteration, imperfect intellectual property distribution, and shortage of interdisciplinary teachers, and proposes optimized paths including agile curriculum updates, improved benefit-sharing mechanisms, and deepened four-party linkage ecosystem. This study aims to provide a replicable paradigm for 3D printing education and industrial cooperation in vocational colleges across China.

Key words: 3D printing; additive manufacturing; industry-education integration; vocational education; talent cultivation; Guangzhou Polytechnic University

1. Introduction

Against the backdrop of the global manufacturing industry's transition toward digitalization and intelligence, additive manufacturing (AM), commonly known as 3D printing, has revolutionized traditional manufacturing paradigms with its advantages of mold-free production, rapid prototyping, and personalized customization. It has been widely adopted in aerospace, biomedical engineering, automotive, cultural and creative industries, and has emerged as a core technology of the new round of industrial revolution. China attaches great importance to the development of the additive manufacturing industry and has issued a series of policies such as **Made in China 2025 and Action Plan for the Development of Additive Manufacturing Industry** to promote industrial scaling-up. Data indicates that China's additive manufacturing industry has maintained sustained and rapid growth, with the size of the 3D printing market in the education sector projected to exceed 13 billion yuan by 2030.

Behind the industrial expansion, talent shortage has become a core bottleneck restricting development. According to estimates by the China Additive Manufacturing Industry Alliance, the industry's talent gap will reach 800,000 by 2025, with a particularly acute shortage of interdisciplinary professionals who possess both design and process capabilities, as well as theoretical and practical expertise. China's traditional 3D printing design education has prominent shortcomings: rigid disciplinary boundaries separate mechanical engineering, materials science, and design disciplines, resulting in a fragmented knowledge structure for students; teaching content is divorced from industrial reality, and training equipment lags behind that of frontline production lines, requiring graduates to undergo long-term retraining before taking up their posts, which increases enterprises' employment costs.

Industry-education integration and school-enterprise cooperation are the fundamental solutions to the dilemmas in talent cultivation, enabling the organic alignment of the education chain, talent chain, industrial chain, and innovation chain. As a public vocational undergraduate university located in the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area, Guangzhou Polytechnic University has carried out distinctive practices in additive manufacturing industry-education integration, leveraging its geographical advantages and accumulated experience in vocational education. It has established the Future Technology Institute of Advanced Design and Additive Manufacturing and co-constructed industrial colleges with leading enterprises, forming a replicable talent cultivation model. Taking this university as a typical case, this paper explores the curriculum restructuring, school-enterprise cooperation mechanisms, and breakthrough paths of 3D printing education in vocational undergraduate universities, providing practical references for similar institutions.

2. Current Status of 3D Printing Design Education and Industrial Development in China

2.1 Industrial Expansion and Structural Contradictions in Talent Supply and Demand

China has established a complete additive manufacturing industrial chain covering materials, equipment, software, and services. The Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area has formed a 100-billion-yuan-level industrial cluster of laser and additive manufacturing, which has become a pillar of Guangdong Province's strategic emerging industries. Industrial development has generated hierarchical talent demands, requiring both technical workers for

equipment operation and high-end technical professionals for structural design, process optimization, and new material research and development.

The talent supply side is seriously mismatched with industrial demand. Traditional engineering education cultivates talents based on single disciplines: students majoring in mechanical engineering lack knowledge of materials, while design students are unfamiliar with manufacturing processes. In contrast, additive manufacturing requires practitioners to master interdisciplinary skills such as digital design, materials science, control engineering, and post-processing. The shortage of interdisciplinary professionals has led to low equipment utilization rates among enterprises, and the dilemma of "having advanced equipment but lacking qualified professionals" has become a key obstacle to industrial upgrading.

2.2 Growth of the Education Market and Transformation of Teaching Models

China's 3D printing education market has experienced explosive growth, with a compound annual growth rate of over 20% in the education sector from 2025 to 2030, reaching 13.24 billion yuan by 2030. Schools at all levels have accelerated the introduction of 3D printing technology, built innovative laboratories and maker spaces, and promoted the transformation of teaching models from theoretical instruction to project-based practical teaching.

School-enterprise cooperation has upgraded from the shallow construction of internship bases to in-depth industry-education integration. Leading enterprises such as Creality 3D and Shining 3D have co-developed curricula, donated equipment, and carried out joint talent cultivation with universities, introducing enterprise technical standards and real projects into campuses. This not only compensates for the shortage of training resources and teachers in schools, but also reserves backup talents for enterprises.

2.3 In-depth Challenges Facing Industry-Education Integration

Current 3D printing industry-education integration still faces universal problems: first, the rapid pace of technological iteration, with the constant emergence of new processes, materials, and equipment, makes it difficult for curriculum updates to keep pace with industrial development; second, the mechanisms for intellectual property rights and benefit distribution are imperfect, as there is a lack of clear agreements on the ownership of joint research and development results and profit sharing between schools and enterprises, which restricts in-depth cooperation; third, there is a shortage of "dual-qualified" teachers, as there are insufficient interdisciplinary teachers with both teaching capabilities and industrial practical experience, which affects teaching quality.

3. Practices of Industry-Education Integration at Guangzhou Polytechnic University

Rooted in the industrial demands of the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area, Guangzhou Polytechnic University has broken the traditional school-running model, deeply embedded itself in the industrial ecosystem, and built a full-chain industry-education integration system in the additive manufacturing field, forming a distinctive practical path.

3.1 Platform Upgrading: Construction of the Future Technology Institute

In 2025, the university was approved to establish the **Future Technology Institute of Advanced Design and Additive Manufacturing**, breaking traditional disciplinary barriers, integrating resources in art design, mechanical manufacturing, and materials engineering, focusing on cutting-edge additive manufacturing technologies and industrial demands, and cultivating interdisciplinary innovative technical and skilled talents. The institute has introduced industrial-grade 3D printing equipment to build a high-level public training base, integrating the training platform with the enterprise R&D platform. Students participate in real projects as "quasi-employees", realizing the seamless connection between the teaching environment and the industrial environment.

3.2 Mechanism Innovation: The "Enterprises Propose Problems, Universities Provide Solutions, the Market Conducts Evaluation" Model

The university has innovated a closed-loop collaborative mechanism oriented toward the real needs of enterprises, subverting the traditional scientific research and teaching models. Enterprises release technical topics based on the pain points in production and research; the university organizes interdisciplinary teams composed of professors, doctors, enterprise engineers, and students to tackle key technical problems; and the R&D results are evaluated based on their market value and industrial application.

In its cooperation with Li-Ning Group, the enterprise put forward the demand for lightweight and personalized customization of sports shoe midsoles. The university team carried out research and development of 4D printed lattice shoes, with students participating in the entire process of 3D scanning, parametric design, material selection, and process optimization. The project overcame key technical challenges and applied for 12 patents, achieving the precise matching between technological innovation and industrial demand.

3.3 Curriculum Restructuring: Dynamic Early Warning and Cutting-Edge Curriculum Updates

In response to the rapid technological iteration, the university has established a "**Red-Yellow-Green Light**" curriculum early warning mechanism: it regularly tracks industrial trends and enterprise needs, eliminating outdated courses (red light), updating courses in need of optimization (yellow light), and supporting cutting-edge courses (green light). Relying on this mechanism, the university has eliminated outdated teaching content and added cutting-edge courses such as *Generative Design*, *Elastomer Material Printing*, and *4D Printing Technology*, integrating frontier technologies such as AI-assisted design and new material printing to ensure that teaching content keeps pace with the industrial frontiers.

3.4 In-Depth Integration: Industrial Colleges and Order-Based Talent Cultivation

The university has co-built the **Li-Ning Sports Industry College** with Li-Ning Group, constructing a close school-enterprise cooperation model. Both parties jointly formulate talent training programs, develop curricula, and build teaching teams. The cooperation has gradually upgraded from order-based classes to industrial colleges: enterprise engineers teach on campus, and students intern at the enterprise during their junior year, realizing the goal of "enrollment equals recruitment, campus entry equals factory entry, and graduation equals employment". Graduates of the Li-Ning order-based classes are in short supply, most of whom enter the enterprise's R&D departments to become technical backbones.

In addition, the university has carried out four-party industry-university-research cooperation with the Guangzhou Future Additive Manufacturing Research Institute and the Greater Bay Area Technology Manager Team, introducing cutting-edge research forces from academician teams to open up the entire chain of "basic research - applied research - achievement transformation", and exploring a new "university-research institute-enterprise-association" linkage model.

4. Practical Effects and Typical Cases

4.1 Significant Improvement in Talent Cultivation Quality

The industry-education integration model enables students to engage with real enterprise projects, greatly improving their practical and innovative capabilities. Over the past three years, the employment rate of graduates from additive manufacturing-related majors has remained above 98%, with most employed in high-end manufacturing enterprises in the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area, and their employment quality is significantly higher than that of

graduates from traditional majors. Students have achieved fruitful innovative outcomes, incubating more than 80 patents and software copyrights, and winning 41 provincial-level and above awards in discipline competitions, including the gold medal in the national "Internet+" Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competition. The quality of talent cultivation has been highly recognized by the industry.

4.2 Enhanced Technical and Social Service Capabilities

The Future Technology Institute has become a regional technical service platform, solving more than 5 key technical problems for cooperative enterprises every year and helping enterprises overcome production pain points. The university's training base is open to small and medium-sized enterprises, providing prototype development and small-batch production services. This not only reduces the innovation costs for small and medium-sized enterprises, but also provides more practical opportunities for students, achieving a win-win situation for all parties. In the cultural and creative field, the university relies on 3D printing technology to help traditional enterprises realize personalized product customization and rapid iteration, expanding their market space.

4.3 Typical Case: R&D of 4D Printed Smart Sports Shoes

In response to the demand for comfort, personalization, and intelligence of sports shoes in the sports and health industry, the university team jointly developed 4D printed smart sports shoes with the enterprise. The interdisciplinary team divided labor and collaborated: design majors were responsible for appearance and interaction, mechanical majors for structural optimization, and materials majors for printing processes. Shape memory materials were adopted to realize the adaptive adjustment of the shoe sole under stress and the dynamic optimization of cushioning performance. Students participated in the core R&D throughout the project, integrating industrial standards with innovative creativity, successfully developing samples and applying for multiple patents, which has become a typical example of industry-education integration empowering technological innovation.

5. Existing Challenges and Optimization Paths

5.1 Main Challenges

1) **Curriculum updates lag behind technological iteration:** New hotspots emerge in the additive manufacturing industry every year, while the long cycle of curriculum development and teacher training makes it difficult for the dynamic early warning mechanism to completely eliminate this lag.

2) **Imperfect benefit distribution and intellectual property mechanisms:** The lack of institutionalized agreements on the ownership of joint R&D results and profit sharing between schools and enterprises affects the enthusiasm of enterprises to invest core resources, as well as the motivation of teachers and students to participate in achievement transformation.

3) **Shortage of interdisciplinary teachers:** Most existing teachers have transitioned from traditional majors, lacking interdisciplinary knowledge and cutting-edge technical capabilities, which makes it difficult to meet the needs of interdisciplinary talent cultivation.

5.2 Optimization Paths and Countermeasures

1) **Construct an agile dynamic curriculum system:** Deepen cooperation with leading enterprises and industrial alliances to establish a normalized technical docking channel; adopt modular curriculum design to quickly update skill modules; introduce enterprise online training and certification systems to compensate for the lag in curriculum updates.

2) **Improve benefit-sharing and risk-sharing mechanisms:** Clarify the ownership of intellectual property rights in school-enterprise cooperation, and increase the proportion of achievement transformation benefits for researchers and students; explore a joint-stock cooperation platform where enterprises contribute equipment and technology, and schools contribute venues and manpower, to build a close community of shared interests.

3) **Deepen the construction of the four-party linkage ecosystem:** Integrate resources from the government, universities, research institutes, and enterprises. The government provides policy and financial support, research institutes provide basic research support, enterprises provide application scenarios, and universities are responsible for talent cultivation and technology transformation, forming a joint force for coordinated development.

6. Conclusion and Prospect

The high-quality development of the additive manufacturing industry is inseparable from the talent support provided by vocational education, and industry-education integration is the core path connecting education and industry. Through the construction of the Future Technology Institute, the innovation of collaborative mechanisms, the restructuring of dynamic curricula, and the in-depth cooperation of industrial colleges, Guangzhou Polytechnic University has solved the problem of disconnection between 3D printing education and industrial demand, realizing the coordinated improvement of talent cultivation, technological innovation, and social services. This provides a replicable and promotable practical sample for additive manufacturing education in vocational undergraduate universities.

At present, industry-education integration still faces challenges in technology, systems, and teachers, requiring the continuous promotion of agile curriculum updates, the improvement of benefit mechanisms, and the construction of the four-party ecosystem. With the deepening of national vocational education reform and the maturity of the additive manufacturing industry, more vocational colleges will explore distinctive industry-education integration models, build a dynamic 3D printing education ecosystem, and provide solid talent support for China's transformation from a large manufacturing country to a manufacturing power.

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